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D.3.2 FIXLAB Second Access Report

Lead Author: François Mirambet (CNRS – C2RMF)

Co-authors: Rémi Petitcol (FSP), Quentin Lemasson (CNRS – C2RMF)

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Authors (Partner)	CNRS – C2RMF		
Responsible Author	Name: François Mirambet	Partner: CNRS – C2RMF	

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Abstract

This deliverable describes the work carried out within WP3 related to providing transnational access to the FIXLAB platform. It contains a report on the access carried out between July 2022 and March 2024, together with a description and an analysis of the scientific work performed within FIXLAB and a reflexive take on the access procedure in preparation for the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS), including the reviewing process and the feasibility check.

Initially composed of 23 stationary non-movable research infrastructures located across 12 countries, the access offer available evolved slightly within the second access period due to changes in the availability of some instrumentation and administrative changes within some providing institutions. In some cases, the description of the offer was clarified on the catalogue of services. Significant reallocation of access units was performed based on the new availability of providers.

After a first access period heavily impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, the second period saw a “catching up” effect in access delivery due to an important backlog of projects granted during the first three calls. This focus on access delivery resulted in a lower number of proposals in the 4th call. From the 5th call onwards, the number of proposals received and granted increased in each call. The 6th call reached the first call numbers, and a successful seventh call was launched in Spring 2023. Despite some significant exceptions, this increase in the number of proposals enabled most platforms to reach their targets and for FIXLAB to significantly outperform its initial targets.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
TNA	Transnational Access
PRP	Peer Review Panel
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
BNC	Budapest Neutron Center
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction: from post-pandemic recovery to complete deployment

While the first IPERION HS access period (April 2020 - June 2022) was almost exclusively dedicated to mitigating the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, the second access period marked the actual start of transnational access activities for most users and providers. The pandemic impacted FIXLAB in different ways: small delays in setting up the catalogue of services and the dashboard for managing the projects, change of communication plans from in-person conferences to 100% digital communication, etc. The first FIXLAB call for access benefited from the momentum of the IPERION CH and the relative optimism of users in Spring 2020. With fewer proposals, the following calls were then strongly impacted by travel restrictions and other restrictions on accessing the facilities. In the meantime, providers were already busy performing the access granted in the first call while dealing with the rest of the backlog caused by closings.

Starting the second access period, the fourth call for access marked a reset in attitudes from pandemic recovery mode to more regular functioning. In several ways, the second-period access calls (call 4 to call 7) behaved the way the whole FIXLAB calls were intended to, with a build-up phase centred around providers with already existing TNA user bases and a progressive inclusion of providers that did not participate in IPERION CH and of new user communities, and a constant increase of the number of projects submitted, granted, and carried out. This translated into a concrete expansion of the research questions and types of objects addressed within FIXLAB, in coherence with topics addressed in the project's Joint Research Activities and networking work packages.

However, this "new start" required significant efforts from the platform coordination and the providers to recreate links with a community that became used to not travelling on-site and to redistribute access units to the providers that were most likely to be able to carry out the access in a much shorter timeframe. This collective effort proved to be fruitful: FIXLAB providers managed not only to reach the initial target when expressed in days despite the closure of some important facilities, but they also managed to provide about 78% more access days thanks to several outperforming providers in less than two years. This spirit of dedication and resilience will be passed on to the future E-RIHS FIXLAB.

This increase in projects submitted, granted, and carried out but also rejected generated new access management challenges. Many of these challenges were addressed directly through increased communication and management activities. These challenges and possible solutions constitute important material for the future launch of E-RIHS ERIC and have been communicated to the E-RIHS Implementation Phase project.

2. The integration of new providers and user communities

When the first access period was mainly driven by the activities of the four “historical providers” (AGLAE, SOLEIL, BNC, ATOMKI) that participated in the previous Integrating Activities and already had established user bases, this second access period showed a marked increase of the activities of the “new providers” and scientific and thematic communities within Heritage Science.

Fig.1: Distribution of projects by platform group (4th to 7th call)

Figure 1 shows the distribution of requests made by different users for the four platform categories for the second access period, including calls for projects from the 4th to the 7th. Groups A and C, which include large platforms and those more dedicated to archaeology and palaeontology, were the most requested, with 37% for the former and 30% for the latter.

The number of requests was lower for platforms dedicated to restoration and preventive conservation (Group D) and for those in Group B, which offer analytical resources that are generally more accessible in research institutions in many countries. The table below reminds us of the detailed clustering of providers in groups by techniques or methods. It was set up for management and communication purposes and does not restrict the kind of topics they can investigate within a transnational access.

Groups	Techniques/Methods	Providers
A	Ion Beam Analysis	AGLAE
		ATOMKI
	Synchrotron techniques	SOLEIL
	Neutrons techniques	BNC
		MLZ/TUM
	Dating	INFN FI
Molecular analysis	HS OMICS	
B	Radiography/Tomography	ITAM
	Optical Spectroscopies	IQFR
	X-ray techniques	IPANEMA
	Mass Spectrometry	VU
	Liquid chromatography	U. Lju.
	Scanning electron microscopy	RAA
HE		
C	Mass spectrometry for isotope ratios	CEZA
	Dating/Electron spin resonance	CENIEH
	Micro-tomography	MNHN
	Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry (TIMS) IT	INFN LNGS
	Ancient DNA Analysis	SciLifelab
	Analysis of ancient biomolecules	BioArch
D	Environmental parameters measurements	UCL
	Simultaneous Thermogravimetry and Differential Thermal Analysis (TG-DTA)	LNEC
	Laser techniques	FORTH

Table 1: The IPERION HS FIXLAB Groups of providers

Fig.2: Number of projects by platform group for the duration of the project

As mentioned in the introduction, a significant change was observed during this second period. Indeed, as shown in graph 2, which summarises the requests received during the entire project (7 calls), the distribution of the requests between the different platform categories has clearly changed. Although requests for group A platforms remain the most frequent, an increase in the requests for groups C and D since the 4th call can be significantly observed, with a very marked trend for the last two calls. The number of requests for groups B and C for these last two calls is of the same order of magnitude as those for group A, which indicates a successful integration of new, usually smaller-sized providers in FIXLAB. It is important to bear in mind that a request can be made to several providers within a single proposal.

A more detailed analysis of these data reveals that this trend is certainly linked to a diversification in the profiles of researchers who have applied for access to FIXLAB platforms. The historical community that has already taken part in the CHARISMA (2009 – 2014, FP7) and IPERION CH (2015 – 2019, H2020) projects still requests platforms such as those dedicated to IBA and neutron techniques, but the greater variety of techniques available in the IPERION HS program has attracted new users. These include specialists in the fields of archaeology and palaeontology, who need access to platforms that can carry out DNA and isotope analysis available in the C group.

It is interesting to note that for many researchers, mainly experienced in art history, access to more “conventional” analytical tools such as SEM and optical spectroscopies proved to meet a real need of these communities. These different analytical tools are not always easily accessible to humanities and social sciences researchers in some countries.

Finally, the proportion of requests to address preventive conservation issues is not negligible, leading many users to submit experiment proposals requiring the implementation of analytical tools available in Group D, which includes techniques for measuring environmental parameters.

The size of the words displayed is proportional to the number of recurrences. The most frequently addressed topics relate to questions about **archaeology**, **provenance** and **conservation**. The list of keywords clearly reveals that users primarily expect to collect new data to improve knowledge of artefacts through accurate sample characterisation.

The main research topics are often related to the study of the manufacturing processes, the know-how of the artists and the craftsmen, and the choice, source and commercial circulation of the natural or synthetic materials used. The main keywords are: **neolithic/palaeolithic**, **archaeometry**, **ancient DNA**, **dating**, **composition**, **paleoproteomics**, **bioarchaeology**, and **geochemistry**.

Some projects submitted by users clearly consider the conservation of artefacts. Keywords such as **pollution**, **degradation**, **preventive conservation**, and **ageing** attest to how much climate change is a real concern for heritage scientists today and reflect the growing importance of the topic within our community.

These research fields often require the use of various complementary techniques available on FIXLAB platforms. Among the most requested techniques are electron spin resonance, dating techniques, lead isotope measurements, neutron techniques, ion beam analysis, and laser techniques. The latter are requested both to characterise materials and as cleaning techniques for restoration. Finally, the materials studied in the various projects are mainly glass, pigments, protein, ceramics, fossils, bone, and DNA.

Although the nature of the research questions brought by FIXLAB users did not fundamentally change from IPERION CH to IPERION HS, several new research areas strongly appeared in this new instalment of FIXLAB, notably within palaeontology and organic chemistry. We believe that this evolution not only reflects a better integration of the different constituent communities of Heritage Science but also, through induced demand and cross-provider access, IPERION HS enabled new, ambitious interdisciplinary projects that address the current challenges faced by the Cultural Heritage community at large.

2.1.1. Diversity of users

Fig.4: Location of the FIXLAB users' institutions

Figure 4 reveals that the majority of users who have requested access to FIXLAB platforms come from EU countries, with no users in the Baltic States, Finland, Slovakia, Luxembourg, and Ireland. Most users work for institutions located in Italy, Portugal, Germany, the United Kingdom, Spain, and France, in descending order. Requests were also received from researchers in non-EU countries such as Egypt, Ukraine, Uganda, South Africa, Canada and the USA. Women were the most represented, making up nearly 60% of users.

Fig.5: Legal Status of the Institution

When submitting a proposal, users provide the status of their institution from a list of codes. There are four possible choices: university, SMEs, research institution, other, and private institutions (other than SMEs).

The data collected on the IPERION HS dashboard and illustrated by Figure 5 shows that 62% of users are affiliated with universities, 23% with research institutions, and 12% with institutions of different status. Only 3% are affiliated with SMEs or other private institutions.

If we look more closely, many researchers are affiliated with Italian universities located in Firenze, Ferrara, Milan, Pisa, and Torino. Spanish universities are also well represented, with those in Barcelona and Valladolid. For other countries, the most cited universities are Cambridge, Zagreb, and Bucharest.

The Research Institutions code covers a wide variety of institutions, mainly museums, including many archaeological museums, archaeological institutes, CNRS and CNR laboratories, and national heritage institutions. Lastly, SMEs are most often private research laboratories.

The OTHER category gathers mainly national Heritage institutions or agencies, such as Heritage Malta or the *Opificio delle pietre dure* (OPD) in Florence. These public institutions that do not identify as primarily research-driven have always played a great role in the E-RIHS community, although they do not exist in every country.

Fig.6: Profile of FIXLAB Platforms Users

A final survey was sent in March 2024 to all FIXLAB providers to collect complementary data about their users and their overall work that was not present in the dashboard. Figure 6 shows the result of the following question: “Are your users "regular users" from IPERION HS, previous projects or own activities?”.

21% of providers declared that most of their users were regular users. This is, for example, the case for the laser platform at FORTH in Greece, the IBA platform at ATOMKI in Hungary and the RAA laboratory in Sweden. Almost half of the providers declared hosting a mix of regular and new users, accounting for 47% of responses. 32% of providers did not have regular users at all, which corresponds to the integration of facilities that either did not significantly engage in Heritage Science before IPERION HS or did not provide access to external users at all before.

This repartition of “new” and “old” users is satisfactory and shows that the future E-RIHS user base has a solid core that came from previous integrating activities or national programmes and also new users for both new and historical providers. Providers declare that the overwhelming majority of users contacted them before submitting their application, either directly or through the IPERION HS helpdesk, with only 20% of platforms indicating that users only contacted them in a minority of cases and 5% have never been contacted.

Half of the FIXLAB providers declared that they provided remote access, and only a small fraction carried out the full access remotely with additional virtual exchanges with the users. After the end of the pandemic, remote access was mainly used for initial tests to come up with the right instrumental parameters or for complementary measurements after a physical visit.

User profiles are very diversified in terms of career stage. Most come from academia as professors or assistant professors, and many users are researchers working in research institutions such as

CNRS and CNR, with a significant participation of post-doc researchers and PhD students in user groups, with sometimes a leading role.

2.2. The added value of providing access

According to the final FIXLAB survey mentioned above and the exchanges during the different Work Package meetings, either during the General Meetings or online, providing transnational access to users within FIXLAB had an overall positive impact on the providers' own institutional scientific activities and networks despite additional administrative work.

In this survey, providers declared providing transnational access within IPERION HS was a huge asset for their institutions. If a lot of accesses carried out were relying on the already acquired experience of the providers, be it knowledge of a specific material or expertise on a technique, it is to be noted that the FIXLAB access was also the occasion for nearly all of the providers to develop new expertise on materials and types of objects and develop new research topics. It also allowed platforms to reach communities that were not traditional users of their techniques.

Addressing challenging questions within TNA projects was also a unique occasion for platforms to refine their analytical methods by improving methodology or making new instrumental developments. Above all, the accesses were also a place of exchange among researchers and triggered new collaborations that will probably evolve into long-term collaborations in the near future.

Results achieved in IPERION HS have already been disseminated with oral and poster presentations at conferences such as Technart2023 in Lisbon. To our knowledge, only a few publications, around ten, have already been released from the experiments conducted in IPERION HS FIXLAB. Nevertheless, our experience from the previous European projects CHARISMA (2009 – 2014, FP7) and IPERION CH (2015 – 2019, H2020), results are usually published in a frame of 3 years. It is thus not surprising that only a few publications are acknowledging IPERION HS FIXLAB accesses because most access delivery was performed in 2023 and early 2024.

Our survey shows that several publications are already being prepared and should be published in the upcoming year. Considering the already published results, teams for the access providers were included as the authors of the publication in more than 75% of them, showing a great implication of the teams in the process of the experiments. In March 2024, no provider was aware of a publication that did not properly acknowledge the project and EC funding.

3. State of access delivery at the end of the project

3.1. Towards providing more than 100% of access units

In July 2022, at the end of the first access period (April 2020 to June 2022), the number of projects granted to users was estimated to fill in 52% of the available access slots, below the 64% target that should have been met on the fourth call. This number of granted projects was not identified as a major shortcoming, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the actual delivery rate of access units was critically low: only 22 projects out of 81 projects in the first three calls had been performed in the first access period, leaving a very significant backlog of granted projects to be performed at the same time at the new ones to be granted in calls 4 to 6.

Clearing the backlog of granted projects became the main FIXLAB priority of the second half of 2022 and, for the most part, of 2023. This situation is reflected in the low number of proposals received in the 4th call when most providers were focused on carrying out experiments and less on communicating about the call. The 5th and the 6th calls showed a progressive improvement in the situation, with more communication, more various projects, and more granted access for each call. In many providing institutions, this positive trend on the demand side increased the backlog of projects to be carried out before 30 September 2023, the then final date of the IPERION HS.

Another challenge also quickly emerged at the beginning of the second access period: the MLZ/TUM neutron facility, which could not perform its first projects due to the COVID-19 pandemic, had to undergo a shutdown for the remaining time of the project. With a foreseen budget of 193 500€, the second largest within FIXLAB, this facility was not in a position to provide any access unit during the whole duration of the project and agreed to redistribute its budget to other FIXLAB providers. SOLEIL Synchrotron and ATOMKI, who had respectively the third and the fifth largest budget, also declared that they would not be able to perform all of their access units due to a decreased availability of their instrumentation caused, low number of requests, and, for ATOMKI, beamline issues. This added significant pressure on the other providers, who had to fit in even more projects in 2023 to meet the project's initial targets.

To address the challenges of carrying out the granted projects and redistributing access units and the corresponding budget, a first redistribution was prepared by the FIXLAB management team, discussed within the access board and validated by the IPERION HS Governing Board during the 3rd Annual Meeting of the project in Cyprus in May 2023. This redistribution plan included two scenarios: redistribution with the then-current project end date and with a 6-month extension. Both options would see most of the MLZ/TUM budget reallocated to CEZA, which was granted several long and complex access projects and had a smaller average daily cost.

At the same time, a survey among providers and exchanges during the WP3 meeting showed that a large majority of providers were in favour of opening an additional call for access to carry out their initial access unit quota while also performing the access units left available by MLZ/TUM, SOLEIL and ATOMKI.

Based on this feedback, the Access Board decided to open a seventh call for ARCHLAB and FIXLAB in Spring 2023. This proved to be the most successful FIXLAB call in the project, with 49 submitted and 34 granted projects.

This 7th call motivated us to apply for a 6-month extension of the project, which the European Commission granted, postponing the project's end date to 31 March 2024. The final reallocation plan was validated by the Access and Governing Boards in the 5th Annual Meeting of the project in Ljubljana in October 2023. The separation of ZVKDS and the University of Ljubljana as two different providers for administrative reasons, the intensive work of CEZA with their newly allocated budget, and the collective efforts of other facilities to reach the initial FIXLAB targets resulted in a 178% completion rate in terms of access units or 169% in terms of days. If we translated the units counted in hours into 8 hours days in order to have the same unit for everyone, 1554 days were performed out of the 920 days of FIXLAB transnational access days planned in the Grant Agreement. This overperformance of 634 days can be attributed to two main factors:

- By reallocating the budget from large-scale facilities with a very high average daily cost to medium-sized facilities, more days could be performed with the same budget. This is especially visible from the reallocation from MLZ/TUM to CEZA and the Slovenian providers.
- In the spirit of the future E-RIHS ERIC, a very large majority of providers agreed to provide some in-kind contributions by providing more access units than originally planned, whether by accepting additional projects at no or reduced costs or by spending more days per project on average when dealing with complex projects that often required testing several instrumental configurations.

The detailed completion rate by provider per reporting period is available in the following table:

Table 2: Completion rate of access units by provider and reporting period

Access provider	Unit of Access	Min. Quantity of access to be provided	Min. Quantity in days	Access Unit Provided in RP1	Access Unit Provided in RP2	Access Unit Provided in RP3	Total Access Units provided	Units remaining	% remaining	Days remaining
1. CNR/INFN (AE) - Florence	day	90	90	45	25	31	101	-11,0	-12%	-11,0
1. CNR/INFN (AE) - Gran Sasso	day	10	10	0	0	44	44	-33,8	-338%	-33,8
10. ATOMKI/EK (BNC)	day	88	88	0	39	48	87	1,0	1%	1,0
10. ATOMKI/ WIGNER	day	13	13	0	10	13	23	-10,0	-77%	-10,0
10. Atomki (BEN)	hour	600	75	0	140	216	356	244,0	41%	30,5
14. RCE/VU	day	2	2	0	0	40	40	-38,0	-1900%	-38,0
17. UEVORA/LNEC	day	40	40	6	7	14	27	13,2	33%	13,2
19. RAA/SciLife Lab	day	15	15	0	0	39	39	-23,8	-159%	-23,8
19. RAA (BEN)	day	5	5	0	4	10	14	-9,0	-180%	-9,0
20. ZVKDS/UL	day	15	15	20	40	85	145	-130,0	-867%	-130,0
20. ZVKDS (BEN)	day	0	0	0	10	13	23	-23,0	0%	-23,0
21. UCL (BEN) - BioArch	day	42	42	0	15	52	67	-25,0	-60%	-25,0
21. UCL (BEN) - Historic England	day	8	8	0	5	4	9	-1,0	-13%	-1,0
21. UCL (BEN) - UCL	day	8	8	0	8	0	8	0,0	0%	0,0
5. ITAM (BEN)	day	9	9	0	0	12	12	-3,0	-33%	-3,0
6. SPK/CEZA	hour	96	12	0	0	2104	2104	-2008,0	-2092%	-251,0
6. SPK/TUM (AE)	day	43	43	0	0	0	0	43,0	100%	43,0
7. CSIC/CENIEH	day	20	20	13	0	68	81	-61	-305%	-61,0
7. CSIC (BEN)	day	30	30	0	14	26	40	-10,0	-33%	-10,0
8. CNRS/ SOLEIL	hour	1085	136	0	168	648	816	269,0	25%	33,6
8. CNRS/MC-CR2MF-AGLAE	day	120	120	35	52	93	180	-60,0	-50%	-60,0
8-CNRS/UBX	day	12	12	0	30	40	70	-58,0	-483%	-58,0
8. CNRS/ULL (AE)	day	12	12	0	0	30	30	-18,0	-150%	-18,0
8. CNRS/MNHN (AE)	day	20	20	0	0	0	0	20,0	100%	20,0
8. CNRS (BEN)	day	45	45	0	7	35	42	3,0	7%	3,0
9. FORTH (BEN)	day	50	50	0	23	40	63	-13,0	-26%	-13,0
Total		2478	920	105,71	597,14	597,14	0,00	-1942,43	-78%	-634,31

3.2 Detailed results of the access calls

The results of all seven calls for access are illustrated in the figure below, and the lists of accepted, rejected, non-feasible, carried out, and cancelled projects are available in dedicated annexes.

Fig.7: Final results of the FIXLAB TNA calls

IPERION HS started with a great first call that benefitted from the dynamic of IPERION CH and the relative optimism of the first months of the pandemic. However, its next calls plummeted due to travel restrictions and shifted priorities worldwide. The year 2022 marked an important change of attitude, observable from both users and providers, with a progressive return to normal, with a first intensive phase of carrying out already granted experiments and a constant increase of submitted and carried out proposals.

Overall, only 13 projects were deemed technically non-feasible by providers. This represents less than 7% of the 204 proposals received and can be attributed to the fact that users usually either contacted the helpdesk or the providers before submitting a proposal or were experienced users with a good knowledge of the requested techniques and instrumentation.

However, the rejection rate of proposals is higher, with 20% of submitted proposals that were not selected for transnational access. Proposals could be rejected at two stages: directly after submission because they did not meet the eligibility criteria or after the scientific evaluation due to a low score (below 60) or simply because they were ranked lower than other proposals and available access spots were already attributed to the highest scoring proposals.

The latest is especially true for the 7th call, where, due to important time and financial constraints, fewer proposals could be granted per provider, thus explaining a much higher rejection rate. The outreach effort carried out by the IPERION HS community was largely successful in bringing new types of users. However, the polysemic nature of “Heritage” and the connection between the Cultural Heritage community and its Natural Heritage counterparts led to the submission of several proposals that did not fall into the scope of the definition of Heritage Science created by ICCROM together with the E-RIHS community:

“Heritage science is the interdisciplinary domain of scientific study of cultural and natural heritage. Heritage science draws on diverse humanities, sciences and engineering disciplines. It focuses on enhancing the understanding, care and sustainable use of heritage so it can enrich people's lives, both today and in the future. Heritage science is an umbrella term encompassing all forms of scientific enquiry into human works and the combined works of nature and humans, of value to people.”

The FIXLAB management team used this definition to assess the eligibility of proposals. Non-compliance with this definition was the leading cause of ineligibility, and it was mostly concerned with projects related to environmental science without any cultural component. It must be noted that FIXLAB, despite these rejections, enabled many projects dealing with “combined works of nature and humans, of value to people” or collections of Natural History Museums. Other ineligible projects were all related to user leaders applying to access within their own countries or with a consortium mainly composed of researchers working in the same country as the requested access provider. Due to the low number of such mistakes and the changing rules in E-RIHS, this has not been a significant issue.

In terms of access delivery, 94% of granted accesses were performed before the end of the project. Most cancellations were made on the provider side due to facility complete or partial shutdowns either due to a facility-wide shutdown (TUM/MLZ facility in Germany) or technical failures occurring in early 2024 (BNC in Hungary). In one case (SOLEIL), one proposal could not be scheduled before April 2024 and will therefore not be claimed within IPERION HS, although the access will still be delivered, and the users will benefit from the same experience.

Two proposals were cancelled by users or their institutions. One was cancelled in 2020 due to travel restrictions and changed institutional priorities, and one was cancelled due to a change in the availability of the object to be analysed. A detailed list of cancelled proposals is available in Annex V.

Finally, two granted proposals involving several were only partially completed due to scheduling issues: the TraPProM project could not be performed on time at BioArch and the SR-Animals project at INFN Florence. These multi-facility projects, despite their great scientific interest, take much longer to plan and carry out and could not be performed on time before 31 March 2024.

4. Improving FIXLAB access in E-RIHS

Throughout the project, regular exchanges were held with access providers to identify difficulties encountered and points of satisfaction, with the aim of improving the services provided to users directly within the project and, when not possible, within E-RIHS. Between 2022 and 2024, four surveys were carried out with providers to better track their needs and activities, better identify the causes of delays, and assess what could be done to improve access delivery (remote access), the access process (the dashboard and the peer-reviewing), to redistribute financial resources, and redirect users to other platforms whenever necessary. The following chapter will analyse the feedback received from providers through surveys and meetings, from users through the User Helpdesk and satisfaction reports, and from the FIXLAB coordination team. This exercise directly feeds into the revision of the E-RIHS Catalogue of services, the dashboard, the user strategy, and the access policy performed with the E-RIHS Implementation Phase project. This dialogue between projects has been constant since the launch of E-RIHS IP in October 2022, culminating in a joint meeting between the two projects in March 2024 in Madrid.

4.1 The IPERION HS Catalogue of Services and Dashboard access

The catalogue of services is the gateway for users to explore the capabilities offered by the FIXLAB platform. However, some users and providers have noted that the current catalogue is challenging to navigate and contains errors that have not been rectified or updated. To address this, explanations with case-study narratives rather than solely technical descriptions could be an option. It is also imperative to provide concise descriptions of service possibilities and limitations, ensuring that users have a clear understanding of what is available. Additionally, linking FIXLAB facilities to providers' websites for clearer information could enhance transparency and accessibility. This would provide users with practical insights into the application of various techniques, facilitating informed decision-making and utilisation of services.

Acknowledging the great value of having a single access and proposal management point, the Dashboard of the FIXLAB platform has garnered mixed opinions regarding its usability. Some users have reported finding it not very intuitive nor easy to navigate, suggesting that improvements are necessary to enhance user experience. One suggestion is the incorporation of an explanatory help function within the Dashboard. Such a feature would serve to clarify complex processes and functionalities, providing users with the guidance they need to navigate the platform more efficiently. By addressing these usability concerns and providing adequate support mechanisms, the Dashboard can become more user-friendly and accessible to all stakeholders.

Managing projects within FIXLAB presents its own set of challenges, particularly concerning access management and communication. One significant issue highlighted by users is the need for multiple provider personnel to access projects on the dashboard. To follow the different steps of a project, both scientific personnel and administrative personnel should have access to the projects since, in some facilities, these tasks are well separated. In facilities providing different techniques, the need

also arose for providers to have access to the project for all the techniques available, not only their own technique. Additionally, there is a pressing need to establish the ability to link previous projects to newly assigned responsible parties. This would not only ensure continuity but also enhance accountability within the project lifecycle. Providers expressed the need for a clearer proposal status and access duration (definition of access units, for example). By addressing these concerns, the platform can streamline project management processes.

4.2 Selection process, post-access duties and advertisement

The evaluation process plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality and feasibility of proposed projects within the FIXLAB platform. However, it has been beset by various challenges, especially delays. Indeed, users have expressed the need for prompt feedback on their project approval or rejection status. To address these issues, several enhancements have been proposed.

In terms of the peer review process, automatically returning reviews to instrument scientists would facilitate transparency and feedback incorporation, enhancing the overall quality of the evaluation process. Furthermore, expanding the pool of referees or allowing users/providers to propose reviewers could expedite the review process, reducing delays and ensuring timely feedback. Lastly, the implementation of anonymous proposal submissions while keeping information on the type of user could be considered to ensure impartiality in the review process, promoting fairness and equity among applicants. These comments and exchanges with both access managers and referees point towards the need to integrate the peer-reviewing process directly into the dashboard in order to streamline the process and provide more transparency to users. This has been communicated to E-RIHS IP and is currently being worked on.

Some providers also expressed some concerns about the feasibility check being performed directly on the dashboard. The first is that sometimes, evaluation of this feasibility was not directly carried out by scientific personnel but rather by administrative personnel or managers. This could be solved by ensuring that several personnel from the same institution can access the dashboard, possibly with different levels of user privileges. The second is that for some proposals, the provider could suggest more adapted experiments and that the modified proposal would follow the normal peer review panel evaluation. The current system only allows for short text comments, and these comments have to be manually transmitted to referees. An update of the feasibility check step is currently being discussed within E-RIHS IP.

The post-access duties section for users could also face a few improvements. Facility providers should receive alert messages informing them of users' submission of final reports and satisfaction surveys, allowing them to stay informed and engaged throughout the process. This way, they would be able to check the quality of the reports and their adequation with the work done. Additionally, and despite their different needs, both administrative and scientific personnel require access to user reports and surveys. This shows once more that all personnel from a provider facility should have

access to the dashboard. Moreover, some users also asked for a satisfaction survey from the providers' perspective on user experience, which could also provide valuable insights.

Some users and providers also called for increased advertisement for the services offered within FIXLAB to enhance their visibility and utilisation, ensuring that users are aware of the full range of capabilities offered by the platform. Despite the significant effort made by the whole IPERION HS project, a largely successful one as shown in Section 2 of this deliverable and the attendance records of the HS Academy events, not all communities within the Heritage Science domain and not every provider or technique benefit from sufficient exposure. The intensification of targeted communication and outreach efforts is planned within E-RIHS in collaboration with national and European stakeholders, including professional and user associations.

5. Conclusion

In many ways, the second FIXLAB access period marked a paradigm shift from the COVID-19 damage control mindset of the first access period to the full deployment of the platform as initially designed in the proposal writing phase. For a great number of providers and an even greater number of users, access delivery only started in 2022. For other platforms, an important backlog of granted projects in the first calls constituted an important challenge at a time when new proposals kept coming in. This situation was also complicated by the unforeseen total or partial unavailability of key large-scale providers, adding pressure on others.

Despite these many challenges, the FIXLAB platform, in collaboration with other platforms and the IPERION HS Joint Research and Networking Activities, successfully met its goal of reaching new communities within the Heritage Science domain through facilities that started the project with no experience in providing transnational access. This is observable through the great variety and wealth of research questions and user profiles of those who benefitted from FIXLAB access and through the feedback of the providers themselves who engaged in the co-creation of knowledge. It also not only reached but surpassed its objectives in terms of reaching its initial target of access units to be delivered, thanks to the unrelenting work of overperforming providers who took in additional access units after a redistribution, often through in-kind work.

The experience of the IPERION HS iteration of FIXLAB has probably been the most challenging one since the creation of FIXLAB in 2004 within the EU-Artech. However, it was also the most ambitious, and it taught us important lessons for the future of E-RIHS ERIC FIXLAB. More importantly, the leap from four access providers to more than twenty-three providers greatly expanded the scientific output of the platform and contributed to bringing new thematic communities into the wider E-RIHS community, thus providing a great contribution to the development of Heritage Science in Europe and beyond.

Annex I: list of selected projects (call 4 to 7)

Acronym	Title	Leader	User Leader country	Access provider	Call number
BalticDiet	Multiproxy biomolecular dietary reconstructions from the Late Iron Age eastern Baltics	Ester Oras	Estonia	BioArch	4
DiRect CesS	Dietary Reconstruction from Cesspits Sediments	Matthew Collins	Denmark	BioArch	4
Diversity in Death	Diversity in Death, Similarity in Life? aDNA analyses of individuals from different burial customs within an Iron Age landscape	Bente Philippsen	Denmark	SciLife Lab	4
LaCeS_FIXLAB	Lipid analysis of Ancient Ceramics in South Asia_FIXLAB	Akshyeta Suryanarayan	Spain	University of Ljubljana	4
MORMO_CHRONO	Mormolo Earlier Stone Age Chronology	Eslem Ben Arous	Germany	CENIEH	4
PePI	Pende Pigments Identification	Aurore Mathys	Belgium	ZVKDS	4
SIBILLA	Simultaneous Ion Beam Investigations for Lapis Lazuli provenance Analysis	Laura Guidorzi	Italy	AGLAE	4
TOMCAT	Roman glass from the black sea: vessels from Tomis and Capidava	Roxana-Nicoleta Bugoi	Romania	BNC	4
TRANSYLVANIAN WINDOW	Color and transparence: IBA analyses on medieval window glass from Transylvania	Roxana-Nicoleta Bugoi	Romania	AGLAE	4
TRAVERTR2022	First U-Th geochronology of the travertine-type carbonate deposits from İzmir Region (western Turkey)	Ismail Isintek	Turkey	CENIEH	4
AIAGM	An archaeometry investigation of ancient glass found in Malta: raw material, trade origin and deterioration processes	Matthew Grima	Malta	AGLAE	5

AnBoRD	Ancient Andean Wooden Boards: Radiocarbon Dating	Samuele Tacconi	United Kingdom	INFN Florence	5
APPALLA	Analysis of Parchment, inks and lead seals of ancient PApal BuLLs from Museum of Santuario della Beata Vergine di Saronno	Giuseppe Politi	Italy	AGLAE	5
CHALCLOOM	A multi-analytical approach on Chalcolithic loom weights from Vila Nova de São Pedro (Portugal) and experimental replicas to establish provenance and production technologies	Rosa Marques	Portugal	BNC WIGNER	5
CHASAP	Characterization of stone tool Surface and sub-surface Alteration Processes during use	Antony Borel	Hungary	AGLAE	5
CuMaHo	Cultural Identity versus Material Homogeneity. Investigations into the composition of copper alloys north of Lake Balaton in the 2nd half of the 7th c. AD	Bendeguz Tobias	Austria	ATOMKI	5
EXPLORSCHIST	Exploring exchanges routes of schist artefacts in Iberian Chalcolithic by micro and non-destructive analytical methods	Ana Luísa Rodrigues	Portugal	BNC WIGNER	5
FILMS ON TOP	Fluorescence Investigations of Laser-Modified Surfaces for improving Photonics Treatments of Oil Paintings	Daniele Ciofini	Italy	CSIC	5
GlazedBricks	Non-destructive characterization of glazed bricks from Ashur and Babylon	Helen Gries	Germany	AGLAE	5
GOLD AND GEMS	COMPREHENSIVE ARCHAEOLOGICAL STUDY OF LATE ANTIQUE GOLD ARTEFACTS INLAID WITH GEMSTONES FROM ROMANIA (5th CENTURY AD)	Rodica Oanță-Marghitu	Romania	AGLAE	5
GREYUNICORN	Analysis of elemental composition for medieval fine grey pottery discovered in Satu Mare	Peter Levene Szocs	Romania	ATOMKI	5
HJ Mts. Metabasites	Hrubý Jeseník Mts. as a potential source region of the metabasite polished stone tools, Czech Republic	Kristýna Trnová	Czechia	BNC	5
ICTI	The Impact of Conservation Treatments on Isotope Analysis	Louisa Allington-Jones	United Kingdom	CEZA	5
INVOSTAG	PGAA, SANS and neutron imaging investigation of votive statuettes made of pottery, belonging to the Academia Georgica Treiensis, Italy	Massimo Rogante	Italy	BNC	5

LANGE	Laser ANalysis of GElatin in photographic negatives and modern paintings	Diego Ivan Quintero Balbas	Italy	CSIC	5
LASART	Laser cleaning of gilded and varnished artefacts	Magdalena Iwanicka	Poland	FORTH	5
PbGlaze	The evolution of lead glaze technologies during the medieval period	Carmen Ting	United Kingdom	VU	5
ReGlaze	Restoration of historic ceramic tiles via glaze lacunae re-glazing using lasers	Maria de Lurdes Esteves Brito	Portugal	FORTH	5
SASHI	Scientific Analysis of Sutton Hoo Inlays	Sue Brunning	United Kingdom	AGLAE	5
SIDIZIN_CHRONO	Sidi Zin Stone Age Chronology	Eslem Ben Arous	Germany	CENIEH	5
STRAIGHT	Study of the Teeth of Renaissance Aristocratic Individuals Grown in different Habitats and Territories	Simona Raneri	Italy	AGLAE	5
TGCP	Tari gold coin project	Alfredo Maria Santoro	Italy	AGLAE	5
TRENCH	Trace element analysis of Late Neolithic and Copper Age copper artefacts from Hungary	Zsuzsanna Siklósi	Hungary	INFN Gran Sasso	5
U-Th calcite dating	Interpretation of the Crustal Deformation of the Central Anatolia and its effect on the cultural heritage in the Central Anatolia: U-Th/ U-Pb calcite dating constraints for Tuz Gölü Fault Zone	GÜLİN GENÇOĞLU KORKMAZ	Turkey	CENIEH	5
VACCAEANGLASS-2	Ion beam analysis of ancient vaccaean glass beads - 2	Javier Pinto	Spain	AGLAE	5
Archeomet Pupak	Archaeometric analysis of shipwreck remains at the Pupak shallows	Jurica Bezak	Croatia	INFN Florence INFN Gran Sasso	6
ARSENIFICATION	Intentional arsenification of prehistoric bronzes: possible production techniques	Marianne Moedlinger	Italy	RAA	6

ByzWall	Laser assisted removal of candles' soot and biodeterioration from Byzantine wall paintings; investigation of the optimal parameters and assessment of the cleaning result.	Ivi Hadjigeorgiou	Cyprus	FORTH	6
CTSRDM	Computed Tomography Scanning of an Ancient Roman Dough from Malta	Roslyn DeBattista	Malta	CENIEH	6
DECOGLASS	Documentation of artistic production patterns and alteration pathologies in glass and glazes through μ -CT	Teresa Palomar	Portugal	CENIEH	6
DVORAK	Deep-UV photoluminescence imaging for the submicron mapping of oil-protein mixtures in Renaissance artworks.	Ilaria Bonaduce	Italy	SOLEIL	6
EAFMB	Elemental analysis of archaeological finds from medieval Bulgaria	Stela Doncheva	Bulgaria	ATOMKI	6
EGILWOOD	Removing dirt from Egyptian gilded wooden artefacts using Laser radiation	Mohamed Moustafa	Japan	FORTH	6
FPB	Fading blues: degradation of modern Western blue papers made out of Prussian blue	Leila Sauvage	Netherlands	IPANEMA	6
FUSH	FUunctionalised SHEet for MS-imaging of art proteins	Leila Birolo	Italy	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	6
GLADIM	Identification of GLAss Disease for Miniatures displaying ongoing mixed materials Deterioration Processes	Maude Daudin-Schotte	Sweden	University of Ljubljana	6
Hall Metals	Archaeometallurgical analyses of bronzes from the famous Iron Age graveyard of Hallstatt, Austria	Mathias Mehofer	Austria	CEZA	6
KRL-GARN	Between Childeric and Theodoric the Great: two outstanding garnet jewellery objects from the Kranj-Lajh cemetery (Slovenia) and their European background	Joan Pinar Gil	Czechia	AGLAE	6
LBA Metalwork	The Missing Link. Identifying the Archaeometallurgical Fingerprint of LBA Metal Workshops	Heide Wrobel Nørgaard	Denmark	CEZA	6
MNI	The metal sources used by the Nabatean	Yehudit Harlavan	Israel	INFN Gran Sasso	6

OPERA	Multispectral luminescence microscopy to map Oil Protein mixturEs in Renaissance Artworks	Ilaria Bonaduce	Italy	IPANEMA	6
P2SFNM	Profiling two skulls from Neolithic Malta	Matthew Grima	Malta	SciLifeLab	6
PrevAlex	Risk Analysis for Preventive Conservation and Human Comfort in the Alexandria Museum of Fine Arts, Egypt	Aly Said	Egypt	UCL University of Ljubljana	6
SAFARI	Secondary Apatite Formation in ARchaeological sites	Cristiano Nicosia	Italy	Historic England	6
SALT	Synchrotron X-Ray Fluorescence Analysis of Salt Formation on Cuneiform Tablets	Mirko Surdi	Belgium	SOLEIL	6
SESAME	Study of the Evolution of Street Art Materials in European urban art	Jacopo La Nasa	Italy	IPANEMA	6
ShowME	Showcases Materials Emission	Lucrezia Barchi	Italy	University of Ljubljana	6
SIBILLA	Simultaneous Ion Beam Investigations for Lapis Lazuli provenance Analysis	Laura Guidorzi	Italy	AGLAE	6
SIDIZIN_CHRONO	Sidi Zin Stone Age Chronology	Eslem Ben Arous	Germany	CENIEH	6
SR-Animals	The Science of Religion: analyses of selected animal remains from Early Rus sacred contexts	Natalia Khamaiko	Germany	SciLifeLab INFN Florence	6
STICK	SculpTure In terraCruda: advancing its Knowledge	Mònica López-Prat	Spain	HS Omics (Bordeaux) ZVKDS University of Ljubljana	6
TraPProM	Tracing populations in Punic and Roman Malta	Bernadette Mercieca	Malta	INFN Florence SciLifeLab	6

				BioArch	
TREMALCA	TRace Elements in MALta Cavalry Armour	Daniel Vella	Malta	SOLEIL	6
VEILS	Face Veils and their Scent as Heritage	Jolanda Bos	Netherlands	UCL University of Ljubljana	6
CERAMIKZ	Ceramic residue analysis for marine and dairy resource detection in the Early Iron Age, KwaZulu-Natal	Emma Loftus	Germany	BioArch	7
ChertNeutron 2.0	Geochemical provenance studies on Middle and Upper Palaeolithic cherts from inland Iberia	Marta Sánchez de la Torre	Spain	BNC	7
COMUN	Coarse ware from the Medieval production site at Utrecht (the Netherlands): a multi-analytical study of forming techniques	Barbara Borgers	Austria	BNC	7
CORE-ISO-GLASS	Reaching to the core: An in-depth isotopic analysis of core-formed glass	Artemios Oikonomou	Greece	VU	7
DAPSIR	news insights on Di-Ammonium Phosphate consolidation: from Synthetic samples to Italian Rocks	Milena Anfosso	Italy	LNEC	7
DeAvibus	The Book of Birds, a medieval bestseller, through the eyes of synchrotron UV–VIS multispectral luminescence	Maria J. Melo	Portugal	SOLEIL	7
DOS	Danmarks Oldest Sheep	Daniel Groß	Denmark	BioArch	7
EAMEDA	Early medieval atypical burials from Poland. Bioarchaeological analysis of selected examples	Olga Dec	Poland	BioArch	7
EnamelAtlas	EnamelAtlas	Jessica Palmer	Belgium	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	7
EQHUM	Equid-human interactions in Medieval Rome: exploring the role and management of equids through zooarchaeological and aDNA analyses.	Chiara Assunta Corbino	Italy	SciLifeLab	7

FAMMM	Foodways among the Maya in Mensabak, Mexico	Eystein Listhaug	Norway	BioArch	7
Fo-Soft	Tetrapod water-to-land transition: a new approach using exceptionally preserved fossil soft tissues	Sophie Sanchez	Sweden	IPANEMA	7
GASP	Cross-Craft Interaction and the Inception of Early Islamic Glazed Ceramic And Silver Production in the Talas River Valley, Kyrgyzstan.	Catherine Klesner	United Kingdom	VU	7
HUDORD2023	Early Medieval Human-Dog coexistence and dietary reconstruction via stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{15}N$ and $\delta^{13}C$)	Eduards Plankajs	Latvia	BioArch	7
IatoAttingitoi	Pottery technologies of Attingitoi (drinking vessels) from the Iron Age site of Monte Iato (Western Sicily): a multi-analytical approach using μ -CT, SANS and experimental archaeology	Birgit Oehlinger	Austria	BNC ITAM	7
IFORA	Investigating Forming techniques and workshop Organisation in the pottery production of Roman Aguntum: an interdisciplinary approach	Martin Auer	Austria	BNC ITAM	7
Iron Ink scrolls	Reading scrolls written in gallus-iron-ink, encapsulated in artefact	Burkhard Schillinger	Germany	BNC	7
ISLAPAP-Talismans	Spectroscopic Analysis of Magical African-ISLAMic PAPER Talismans Collection at the Slovene Ethnographic Museum, Slovenia	Marko Frelih	Slovenia	CSIC	7
KBFI	Khpu Bast Fibre Identification	Lucrezia Milillo	United Kingdom	RAA	7
LaCOxPaS	Laser Cleaning of Oxalate patinas on Painting Surfaces	Ilaria Pecorelli	Italy	FORTH	7
LATERAL	Laser micro-cleaning Treatment for External Ion Beam Analysis of Lapis lazuli	Marta Magalini	Italy	AGLAE	7
Le Rouge et le Rose	Le Rouge et le Rose. Colors based on the alizarin core from the Middle Ages to the 19th-century disclosed by Imaging techniques	Paula Nabais	Portugal	IPANEMA	7
MAREFASUP	CALCULATION OF THE REGIONAL MARINE RESERVOIR EFFECT IN THE AEGEAN SEA DURING THE UPPER PALAEO-LITHIC PERIOD	Yorgos Facorellis	Greece	INFN Florence	7

MCHPAL	Characterizing morphological and chemical heterogeneities in unique fossils from the Brazilian paleontological heritage	Bruno Becker Kerber	United States	IPANEMA	7
NACH	Non-destructive analysis for the characterisation of cultural heritage	Valeria Comite	Italy	CSIC	7
P.O.L.V.M. TEST	Preservation of lipids on various material - Test samples	Ármann Guðmundsson	Iceland	BioArch	7
palaeoBLUE	palaeoBLUE: Archaeometric analyses of blue traces on a Palaeolithic sandstone object	Isobel Wisher	Denmark	AGLAE RAA SOLEIL	7
Paw	Palaeoproteomic Analysis on Whales	Youri van den Hurk	Norway	BioArch	7
PRECISOPS	Understanding the precipitation methods of early-SOPs by characterisation of the inorganic substrate	Sanne Berbers	Netherlands	SOLEIL	7
REPLAY	Recovering audio from degraded analogue tapes using X-ray magnetic dichroism	Sebastian Gliga	Switzerland	SOLEIL	7
ROMAN WINDOW	Shining through: revealing the chemical composition of roman and late antique window panes	ROXANA-NICOLETA BUGOI	Romania	BNC	7
TCO	The first Christians of Odense, Denmark	Kirstine Haase	Denmark	SciLifeLab	7
TIMELY	Tracing Moravian celt mobility by strontium isotope analysis	Kevin Salesse	Czechia	VU	7
STURGEONED	Treasures of the Depths: Exploring the Possibilities of Sturgeon identification by ZooMS	Teodora Mladenović	Serbia	BioArch	7

Annex II: list of rejected projects (call 4 to 7)

Acronym	Title	Leader	User Leader country	Access provider	Call number
ICTP	The impact of conservation treatments on proteomics analysis	Louisa Allington-Jones	United Kingdom	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	4
ND_pistiros	Non destructive study of the structural and compositional variations on marbles finds from ancient Pistiros via neutron diffraction technique.	Ioannis Siouris	Greece	TUM	4
UM	Uzun Mera research project	Darko Stojanovski	North Macedonia	CENIEH	4
BLACKSEA-RISE	Geochronology of the late Pleistocene Black Sea coastal sedimentary record	Mehmet Korhan Erturaç	Turkey	CENIEH	5
PYRORAG	Research of geological and/or archeological signs on the pyroclastic succession of KPT located on Bodrum Peninsula (Mugla,Türkiye)	Cennet Ulukavak	Turkey	CENIEH	6
BIMFColl	Development of an HBIM Framework for the Preventive Conservation of Cultural Heritage Collections	Daniel Duran-Romero	Spain	UCL	7
BLACKSEA	Absolute Dating of the late Pleistocene-Holocene Sea-level Changes of the Black Sea	Mehmet Korhan Erturaç	Turkey	CENIEH	7
CLIMAARCH_GR	Assessing the Impact of Climate Change and Human Activities on the Deterioration of Greek Archaeological Sites Built with Marble: Monitoring Models for Natural Disasters, Anthropogenic Factors, and Gradual Environmental Changes	Mei Lin Lyu	Greece	RAA	7
COmics	Cooking pit analysis by lipidomics and proteomics	Bente Philippsen	Norway	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	7
DateRhine	Dates and rates of the Quaternary evolution of the Middle Rhine inferred from electron spin resonance dating	Melanie Kranz	Switzerland	CENIEH	7
GRISOL	Influence of solar radiation in the alteration of grisaille	Teresa Palomar	Spain	CENIEH	7

HIGUER-OBS 1	Provenance analysis of the obsidian from the archaeological site El Higuero I	Uriel Alan Olvera Portilla	Mexico	AGLAE	7
INTERACT	Chemical interactions between lipids and proteins in mixed media paint binders	Ilaria Bonaduce	Italy	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	7
Meta-ICP-MS	Inferring in the mobility of prehistoric societies by ICP-MS characterization of metamorphic rocks	Cristian Emens Aranas	Spain	VU	7
PARTICULE	Dust study in Napoléon III Apartments in Louvre Museum	Joelle Le Roux	France	UCL	7
PENCA-MFA	Provenance study of early Egyptian and Nubian copper alloy artefacts from the collections of the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston	Jiri Kmosek	Czechia	VU	7
SALTMUNTS	Analysis and monitoring of the salts in the Roman villa of Els Munts	Maria Jose Gracia	Spain	UCL	7
toMETAL BA	Tracing the origin of metal in the Early Bronze Age Poland	Kamil Nowak	Poland	VU	7
WATCH	Wood ultrAsTructure: Combined imaging analysis for the CHaracterization of age-induced changes	Alice Dal Fovo	Italy	LNEC ZVKDS SOLEIL	7
WDTD	When did they die? – 14C perspectives on wetland animal deposit	Pernille Pantmann	Denmark	INFN Florence	7

Annex III: list of non-feasible projects (call 4 to 7)

Acronym	Title	Leader	User Leader country	Access provider	Call number
ICTI	The impact of conservation treatments on isotope analysis	Louisa Allington-Jones	United Kingdom	CEZA	4
NICER	Neutron-based Imaging CEramic Residues	Michael Buckley	United Kingdom	BNC	4
SPINOSO	Study of Particulate matter in INdoor air and of powder deposit On painted surface of wooden statues of Santuario della Beata Vergine dei Miracoli of Saronno (VA) - Italy.	Giuseppe Politi	Italy	AGLAE	4
PILHRPCVGHOCOTL	Possibilities of implementation of laser with high repetition of pulses in conservation of polychrome, varnished and gilded heritage objects - comparison with other types of laser.	Anna Faron	Poland	FORTH	5
ANTRO	Analysing the Network of Toirano caves: Research On the stratigraphic sequences	Ivano Rellini	Italy	CENIEH	6

Annex IV: list of carried-out projects (all calls)

Acronym	Provider	Call	Access Period
ARMOIRE	AGLAE	1	1 st
ARTILE	LNEC	1	1 st
ATTIA	AGLAE	1	1 st
CHAGRI	CSIC	1	1 st
ChaSAP	AGLAE	1	1 st
FLORES	ATOMKI	1	1 st
GEOCOMLES	AGLAE	1	1 st
JMB-NCHT	AGLAE	1	1 st
LionMan	AGLAE	1	1 st
MAILCOM 2021	BNC	1	1 st
MAL-GLASS-ROM	AGLAE	1	1 st
MeCaMi	AGLAE	1	1 st
MOSAICS	BNC	1	1 st
SIBILLA	AGLAE	1	1 st

SOOCA	AGLAE	1	1 st
T.HER.A	LNEC	1	1 st
VACCAEANGLOSS	AGLAE	1	1 st
COPPEREAST	AGLAE	2	1 st
EANFEM	ATOMKI	2	1 st
LaSi	FORTH	2	1 st
OSIRIS	AGLAE	2	1 st
CHAGRI 2	CSIC	3	1 st
AMSACHRONO	CENIEH	1	2 nd
CCCHRM	Univ. Ljubljana	1	2 nd
CH_MPPM	Univ. Ljubljana IPANEMA	1	2 nd
ChMoIn	INFN Florence BioArch	1	2 nd
ColourAs	RAA	1	2 nd
DANAGAA	AGLAE	1	2 nd
DiODuCat - F	INFN Florence CENIEH	1	2 nd
ECME Abu Rawash	AGLAE	1	2 nd

FINGERCHALC	WIGNER BNC	1	2 nd
IVORIST	WIGNER BNC	1	2 nd
LaMPaplas	FORTH	1	2 nd
NeutronChert	BNC	1	2 nd
RHINESR	CENIEH	1	2 nd
ROMAN GLASS @ BLACK	BNC	1	2 nd
SpIDE	HS OMICS (Lille)	1	2 nd
BRASS	AGLAE	2	2 nd
Color-Bergs	AGLAE	2	2 nd
Egyptian Lapis Lazul	BNC	2	2 nd
MmKc	INFN Florence ZVKDS	2	2 nd
OLYXRD	SOLEIL	2	2 nd
Shell POP	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	2	2 nd
SIBILLA	AGLAE	2	2 nd
AIAGM	CEZA SOLEIL	3	2 nd
CELLULO3D	IPANEMA	3	2 nd

CEMENTOmics	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	3	2 nd
CropDisperSW	BioArch	3	2 nd
DUV4Manuscripts	SOLEIL	3	2 nd
FinCo	FORTH BioArch	3	2 nd
GEOCOMLES2	AGLAE	3	2 nd
IDeLA	ZVKDS	3	2 nd
MELB	BNC	3	2 nd
MMM:khipu	Historic England	3	2 nd
REMIXIS	ZVKDS IPANEMA AGLAE	3	2 nd
Rho-Glass	BNC	3	2 nd
SMELIBS	CSIC	3	2 nd
TANGLE	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	3	2 nd
UCSAEM	CEZA	3	2 nd
BalticDiet	BioArch	4	2 nd
DiRect CesS	BioArch	4	2 nd
Diversity in Death	SciLifeLab	4	2 nd

LaCeS_FIXLAB	Univ. Ljubljana	4	2 nd
MORMO_CHRONO	CENIEH	4	2 nd
PePI	ZVKDS	4	2 nd
SIBILLA	AGLAE	4	2 nd
TOMCAT	BNC	4	2 nd
TRANSYLVANIAN WINDOW	AGLAE	4	2 nd
TRAVERTR2022	CENIEH	4	2 nd
AIAGM	AGLAE	5	2 nd
AnBoRD	INFN Florence	5	2 nd
APPALLA	AGLAE	5	2 nd
CHALCLOOM	BNC WIGNER	5	2 nd
CHASAP	AGLAE	5	2 nd
CuMaHo	ATOMKI	5	2 nd
EXPLORSCHIST	BNC WIGNER	5	2 nd
FILMS ON TOP	CSIC	5	2 nd
GlazedBricks	AGLAE	5	2 nd

GOLD AND GEMS	AGLAE	5	2 nd
GREYUNICORN	ATOMKI	5	2 nd
HJ Mts. Metabasites	BNC	5	2 nd
ICTI	CEZA	5	2 nd
LANGE	CSIC	5	2 nd
LASART	FORTH	5	2 nd
PbGlaze	VU	5	2 nd
ReGlaze	FORTH	5	2 nd
SASHI	AGLAE	5	2 nd
SIDIZIN_CHRONO	CENIEH	5	2 nd
STRAIGHT	AGLAE	5	2 nd
TGCP	AGLAE	5	2 nd
TRENCH	INFN Gran Sasso	5	2 nd
U-Th calcite dating	CENIEH	5	2 nd
VACCAEANGLOSS-2	AGLAE	5	2 nd
Archeomet Pupak	INFN Florence INFN Gran Sasso	6	2 nd

ARSENIFICATION	RAA	6	2 nd
ByzWall	FORTH	6	2 nd
CTSRDM	CENIEH	6	2 nd
DECOGLASS	CENIEH	6	2 nd
DVORAK	SOLEIL	6	2 nd
EAFMB	ATOMKI	6	2 nd
EGILWOOD	FORTH	6	2 nd
FPB	IPANEMA	6	2 nd
FUSH	HS Omics (Bordeaux)	6	2 nd
GLADIM	Univ. Ljubljana	6	2 nd
Hall Metals	CEZA	6	2 nd
KRL-GARN	AGLAE	6	2 nd
LBA Metalwork	CEZA	6	2 nd
MNI	INFN Gran Sasso	6	2 nd
OPERA	IPANEMA	6	2 nd
P2SFNM	SciLifeLab	6	2 nd

PrevAlex	Univ. Ljubljana UCL	6	2 nd
SAFARI	Historic England	6	2 nd
SALT	SOLEIL	6	2 nd
SESAME	IPANEMA	6	2 nd
ShowMe	Univ. Ljubljana	6	2 nd
SIBILLA	AGLAE	6	2 nd
SIDIZIN_CHRONO	CENIEH	6	2 nd
SR-Animals	CEZA INFN Florence SciLifeLab	6	2 nd
STICK	HS Omics (Bordeaux) Univ. Ljubljana	6	2 nd
TraPProM	INFN Florence SciLifeLab	6	2 nd
TREMALCA	SOLEIL	6	2 nd
VEILS	Univ. Ljubljana	6	2 nd
CERAMIKZ	BioArch	7	2 nd
COMUN	BNC	7	2 nd
CORE-ISO-GLASS	VU	7	2 nd
DAPSIR	LNEC	7	2 nd

DOS	BioArch	7	2 nd
EAMEDA	BioArch	7	2 nd
EnamelAtlas	HS Omics (Lille)	7	2 nd
EQHUM	SciLifeLab	7	2 nd
FAMMM	BioArch	7	2 nd
Fo-Soft	IPANEMA	7	2 nd
GASP	VU	7	2 nd
HUDORD2023	BioArch	7	2 nd
IatoAttingitoi	BNC ITAM	7	2 nd
IFORA	BNC ITAM	7	2 nd
ISLAPAP-Talismans	CSIC	7	2 nd
KBFI	RAA	7	2 nd
LaCOxPaS	FORTH	7	2 nd
LATERAL	AGLAE	7	2 nd
Le Rouge et le Rose	IPANEMA	7	2 nd
MAREFASUP	INFN Florence	7	2 nd

MCHPAL	IPANEMA	7	2 nd
NACH	CSIC	7	2 nd
P.O.L.V.M. TEST	BioArch	7	2 nd
palaeoBLUE	RAA AGLAE SOLEIL	7	2 nd
PAW	BioArch	7	2 nd
PRECISOPS	SOLEIL	7	2 nd
REPLAY	SOLEIL	7	2 nd
STURGEONED	BioArch	7	2 nd
TCO	SciLifeLab	7	2 nd
TIMELY	VU	7	2 nd

Annex V: list of cancelled projects (all calls)

Acronym	Provider	Call	Access Period	Justification
ESAM	UCL	1	1st	Cancelled by the user's institution due to travel COVID-19 travel restrictions and changed priorities
NAARB	TUM	1	1st	Facility shutdown
NurBronze	TUM	1	1st	Facility shutdown
STEELENCE	TUM	1	1st	Facility shutdown
INVOSTAG	BNC	5	2nd	Cancelled by the user because the object was no longer available
ChertNeutron 2.0	BNC	7	2nd	Initially scheduled in early 2024, cancelled due to beamline issues
DeAvibus	SOLEIL	7	2nd	Scheduled after 31 March 2024, will not be claimed within the project
Iron Ink scrolls	BNC	7	2nd	Initially scheduled in early 2024, cancelled due to beamline issues
ROMAN WINDOW	BNC	7	2nd	Initially scheduled in early 2024, cancelled due to beamline issues